

The Significance of A. Orinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People

Burkhanov I. M.¹

¹ Graduate student of Fergana State University. Uzbekistan

Abstract:

The article provides brief comments on the history of the Uzbek historian's introduction into scientific circulation of handwritten sources that are important in the study of the history of the Turkic peoples.

Keywords: Turks, people, Amir Temur, manuscript, translation.

Each sovereign state has its own unique history and culture. The president of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoev stated that the real creator and creator of this history and culture are the people of this country [1.1.]. After our state literally became independent, there were radical changes in the socio-political, economic and cultural life of our people.

We all know very well what difficult times and difficult trials there have been in the thousand-year history of the Uzbek people. At the same time that the history of Uzbek statehood is being studied with great interest by the historians of the world, the history of our country was negatively exaggerated by the Soviet historians.

Due to Soviet ideology, obstacles to unbiased coverage of the history of Uzbekistan have increased, despite the fact that there are difficult times for real historians academician Yakhyo Ghulomov, I. Mominov, B. Akhmedov, well-known source scholar A.Urinboev and other outstanding historical scientists have become an example for today's youth by showing spiritual courage and moving forward towards their goals.

The life and scientific heritage of every scientist who made a great contribution to the study of the history of Uzbekistan always arouses interest in people. In particular, A.Urinboev is an

accomplished historian, orientalist, devoted pedagogue, public figure who knows Uzbek, Russian, Arabic, and Persian languages perfectly at the same time. Today, in the history of Uzbekistan, young people are remembered as an enviable person and it creates a need to study the scientist's scientific heritage. Today, researching the scientific heritage of scientists who contributed to the development of the history of Uzbekistan and teaching it to young people is considered one of the tasks in understanding the national identity.

Amir Temur and the history of the Timurid state, the research of sources providing information on the political, social, economic, and cultural life of the peoples who lived in the regions of Central Asia in the XIV-XV centuries occupied a central place in A.Urinboev's scientific activity. This direction is also divided into different seasons:

- In 1991, A. Urinboev completed and published a scientific study entitled "Giyosiddin Naqqosh's Chinese travelogue" [3.1.]. The special feature of this valuable source, which provides information on the history of diplomatic relations and embassy relations of the Timurid state, is that it has its place in the science of history as the only manuscript from which full information about the Chinese state can be obtained. It contains a chronological and territorial map of the embassies sent by the Timurid rulers to the Chinese state and diplomatic relations, and interesting historical information about the trip. On February 25, 1420, these ambassadors, together with the Chinese ambassadors, set off from Samarkand, passing through Tashkent, Sayram and Ashpara regions, they will reach the territory of Mongolia on April 25.

At this time, there was a period when political disagreements intensified in Mongolia, and enmity arose between Uwais Khan and Sher Muhammad Oghlan. Envoys of the Timurid Empire entering a politically turbulent region are naturally confused. However, Hudaidad, one of the Dughlat emirs who had a great position in Mongolia, came to them and told them that there was no danger and that they could continue their journey. Only after that, the ambassadors will reach Yulduz pasture on June 10, 1420, Turfon on July 11, 1420, and Karakhoja regions on July 16. A special group sent by the Chinese emperor will meet the ambassadors on July 21, that is, they will write down their names. After that, the ambassadors of the Timurids will be welcomed positively by the Chinese state and citizens. The diplomatic relations there were recorded by Ghiyosiddin Naqqosh. According to his information, the ambassadors sent by Shahrukh were received with great respect and attention by the Chinese emperor [4.1.]. The letters of Shahrukh Mirza and his emirs to the Chinese ruler were wrapped in a piece of yellow satin and presented to the emperor. Timurid ambassadors sent to China arrived in Herat in 1422. As a result of these embassy relations, the main focus is on trade and economic relations, and internal and external trade between the countries has developed.

In 1991, A.Urinboev published an article containing valuable information on the history of construction and monuments in Central Asia from the end of the 14th century to the beginning of the 15th century. The work "Zafarnama" by Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi was taken as a basis for this article [5.1.]. This article by A.Urinboev also serves as a useful study for scholars in the field of architecture and building construction.

In 1994, in connection with the 600-year jubilee of one of the Timurid princes, the astronomer and scientist Mirza Ulug'bek, scientific events were organized and held. In this regard, A.Urinboev actively participated in many journals and scientific conferences with his scientific research [6.1.]. The fact that one of these articles was published in French, one in Russian, and another in Uzbek is evidence of the high linguistic erudition of the scientist.

There are also scientific researches of A.Urinboev on the history of Naqshbandi doctrine, which provide valuable information about the development of the Naqshbandi sect and its manifestations in contrast to various sects of Islam. For example, in the article entitled "Reflection of Naqshbandi

doctrine in 15th century cUrrespondence" published in 1994, it was mentioned about Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Husayn Boygaro, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, among the majUr representatives of this doctrine. Especially, in the letters of Abdurahman Jami and Alisher Navoi, interesting infUrmation is given about the explanation of the rules of the Naqshbandi doctrine developed under the slogan "Dast ba kUru dil ba YUR" such as "Khilvat dar anjuman, safar dar vatan, nazar bar qadam, hush dar dam" [7.1.]. It is no secret that the name of this sect is related to Bahauddin Naqshbandi.

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